

BUSINESS PLAN WHILE DEVELOPING AN INVESTMENT PROJECT

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Abstract: The definition of the business plan's significance for the organization's investment strategy is provided in the article. The organization's investment planning process, the goals and functions of a business plan, and the methodology used to realize the investment project's business plan are all given. The importance of the topic of this paper is explained by the fact that any small business owner, whether new to the industry or experienced, needs to accurately predict the sources of the resources that will be needed in the near future, including financial, material, labor, and intellectual resources, but also to be capable of precisely and effectively evaluating how well such resources are used in the production processes. use of these resources in the company's commercial operations, production processes, and product development.

Key words: economic efficiency, investment strategy, and company plan.

The importance of business planning as a tool for organization and coordination management in the current economic climate is demonstrated by its ability to establish a course of action from start to finish. Business planning is based on the methodical application of methods for attaining efficiency in the implementation of any form of business operations and keeping acceptable levels of risk, regardless of the commercial projects that are done.

An investment project's business plan is a strategy document that outlines all the key elements of the future commercial organization, evaluates and analyzes risks, and

suggests solutions. Profitability and investment feasibility are ascertained by a well-written business strategy. Calling the business plan the foundation of the organization's management structure is not hyperbole. Mobilization is continuously encouraged by the very process of creating and carrying out a business plan, which involves a thorough examination of organizational and economic concerns. Such a strategy may be intended to secure a loan, draw in investment, establish strategic and tactical guidelines, evaluate the organization's position in the market, attain the required sales volume outcomes, etc. The business plan is a comprehensive strategy for running a company.

Regardless of its functional orientation, a business plan is a multifaceted management tool that can be used to solve strategic and tactical tasks. These tasks include identifying potential business opportunities, analyzing the organization's strengths and weaknesses, forming investment objectives for the planned period, and conducting organizational, managerial, financial, and economic assessments of the organization's condition.

An investment business plan serves as both a vital tool for assessing project and investment decisions and an objective evaluation of the outcomes of an organization's investment activity. Such a strategy identifies the key elements of the business's operations, predicts how the implementation of the investment decision will affect its financial situation, and assesses the effectiveness and timeliness of investment implementation. As a result, the investment business plan serves as a search, study, and project work all at once.

The purpose of planning is to accomplish specific objectives. For clarification, let's get acquainted with Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Objectives of creating a business plan

To plan the investment activity of an organization means to draw up a plan for its development and subsequently control its implementation. Its implementation, assessing its efficiency at each stage of implementation. The basis of investment business planning is the processing of information on the justification of the forthcoming actions and the determination of the best ways to achieve the intended goals. The main goal of investment business planning is to determine the most effective direction of development, to determine the most effective direction of development organization and, on the basis of its

economic justification and step-by-step instructions, to implement investments taking into account acceptable risks.

From this main objective a number of private objectives of investment business planning:

- Coherence of the objectives of the business units (as lower-order objectives objectives) with the objectives set out in the business plan (as higher-order objectives);
- taking preventive measures to avoid potential financial problems (e.g., avoiding a reduction in the profitability of the business by diversifying assets); and the profitability of the business by diversifying assets);
- Coordinating the business plan with the organization's financial strategy to avoid unforeseen impacts on each other, preventing the realization of investment decisions;
- preparation of the investment decision by means of its economic justification in the investment business plan;
- determination of the main methods of control over the realization of the of the investment business plan;
- informing the personnel about the chosen directions of the organization's development organization and possible correction of their job descriptions for the purpose of coordination of actions in the course of implementation of the investment business plan.

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